

3 : 5 Dibromosalicyl-azide : a Reagent for Identification of Aminoacids

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THE reactivity of Salicyl azide¹ and 5-Chlorosalicyl azide² towards amino acids was found to be encouraging; so a new azide with different combination of bromo group substituents namely 3 : 5 dibromo was synthesised and its reactivity to several amino acids has been investigated. These derivatives were crystalline with sharp melting points and could be separated from each other by thin layer chromatography. In quantitative estimation of amino acid derivatives by thin layer chromatography approximately 80% yield was found.

Lellmann and Grothmann³ and Robertson⁴ prepared 3 : 5 dibromo salicylic acid by different methods and the yield of acid was never more than 35%. Other routes for the preparation of 3 : 5 dibromosalicylic acid are also indicated in the literature (Lassar-cohn and Schultze, and Ullmann and Kopetschni⁵), but the yield of product is not satisfactory. Peratoner⁶ prepared methyl 3 : 5 dibromosalicylate with hydrochloric acid. C. N. Haksar and R. D. Wankhade⁷ prepared it by esterification of 3 : 5 dibromosalicylic acid using Fischer-Speier method. It was converted into 3 : 5 dibromosalicyl hydrazide by 60% hydrazine hydrate. This hydrazide was readily converted into azide by the action of sodium nitrite. These azides give crystalline derivatives with amino acids with sharp melting points.

Thus 3 : 5 dibromosalicyl azide was found to be a prospective reagent for identification of amino acids.

temperature for one hour. The reaction mixture was cooled in ice and poured into an excess of ice-cold water, when a bulky white precipitate of methyl 3 : 5 dibromosalicylate was obtained along with a small quantity of methyl 5-bromosalicylate. The precipitate was filtered and dried (yield 16 g).

This crude product (10 g) in glacial acetic acid (30 ml) was again subjected to bromination with bromine (5.2 g) in glacial acetic acid (20 ml) as above. This gave a precipitate of pure methyl 3 : 5 dibromo salicylate. It was filtered at the pump, dried and crystallised from aqueous methanol giving colourless needles, m. p. 148° (Lit 148°, 149°, 156°), yield 11 g.

Analysis : Found Br. 52.30%

 $C_8H_6O_3Br_2$ requires Br 51.61%

3 : 5 Dibromosalicyl hydrazide (ii) : Methyl dibromosalicylate (2 g) was dissolved in methanol (100 ml) and 60% hydrazine hydrate (5 ml) was added. The mixture was refluxed over a water bath for 20 minutes. The solution was diluted with water and cooled. To the cold solution a few millilitres of dilute acetic acid were added, when a voluminous white solid separated. It was filtered and washed with methanol. Yield 1.8 g, crystallised from hot water giving needles, m. p. 217° (decomp.)

Analysis : Found C 27.07%, H 2.23%, N 9.53%,
Br 41.47%. $C_7H_6O_3N_2Br_2$ requires C 27.09%, H 1.93%,
N 9.032%, Br 51.61%.

3 : 5 Dibromosalicylazide (iii) : Dibromosalicyl hydrazide (1.5 g) was dissolved in normal nitric acid (15 ml) and water (30 ml), when a clear solution was obtained. This was cooled in ice and 1N solution of sodium nitrite (20 ml) was

Experimental

Dibromosalicylate (i) : The preparation was carried out according to method of Cahours⁸.

Ice cold solution of bromine (16 g) in glacial acetic acid (20 ml) was added slowly in small portions to an ice-cold solution of methyl salicylate (10 g) in glacial acetic acid (30 ml) with thorough shaking. Bromination was carried out at room

temperature added drop by drop with frequent shaking. The mixture was allowed to stand in ice for one hour, when an oily substance that had separated in the beginning solidified. It was filtered and washed with ice cold water. It was unstable and should therefore be used as quickly as possible.

General method of coupling 3 : 5 dibromosalicyl azide with different amino acids :

The moist dibromosalicyl azide from above⁸ was

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added in the solution of amino acids in 1N caustic soda solution and water. The mixture was shaken and allowed to stand in ice.

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S. No.	Amino acid	Molecular formula	M.P. °C	Analysis%	
				Found	Required
1.	Glycine	C ₉ H ₇ O ₄ NBr ₂	171	C 30.2 H 2.0 N 4.01	C 30.9 H 1.98 N 3.96
2.	Leucine	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ NO ₄ Br ₂	160	C 39.1 H 3.6 N 3.4	C 39.7 H 3.3 N 3.1
3.	Lysine	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₆ N ₂ Br ₄	115	C 34.4 H 2.5 N 3.3	C 34.1 C 2.0 N 3.1
4.	Isoleucine	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ NO ₄ Br ₂	Above 260	C 38.2 H 3.5 N 3.2	C 38.2 H 3.6 N 3.6
5.	Valine	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ NO ₄ Br ₂	Above 240	C 36.2 H 3.1 N 3.3	C 36.4 H 3.2 N 3.5
6.	Alanine	C ₁₀ H ₉ NO ₄ Br ₂	Black on 235	C 32.4 H 2.6 N 3.9	C 32.6 H 2.8 N 3.8
7.	Methionine	C ₁₃ H ₁₈ NO ₄ Br ₂	155	C 33.6 H 3.2 N 4.0	C 33.7 H 3.0 N 3.6
8.	Glutamine	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₆ N ₂ Br ₂	185	C 33.5 H 2.9 N 6.0	C 33.9 H 2.8 N 6.6
9.	Glutamic acid	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₆ NBr ₂	188	C 34.0 H 2.2 N 3.4	C 33.8 H 2.5 N 3.2
10.	Asparagine	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ O ₆ N ₂ Br ₂	142	C 32.5 H 2.5 N 3.6	C 32.2 H 2.4 N 3.4
11.	Cysteine	C ₁₀ H ₉ O ₄ NsBr ₄	140	C 30.2 H 2.4 N 4.0	C 30.0 H 2.2 N 3.8

All the melting points are uncorrected.

The liquid was filtered and the clear filtrate was extracted with ether to remove the unchanged azide. It was then acidified with dilute sulphuric acid. The acid formed during the reaction was immediately extracted with ethyl acetate in which it was soluble at room temperature. The ethyl acetate was then dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the excess of solvent was removed by distillation under reduced pressure. On concentration the solid separated.

Following the above procedure a number of derivatives with amino acids were obtained and are given in the table above :

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A new Method for Determination of Solubility Product of Silver Bromide

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WHEN two solutions of uni-univalent electrolytes having a common ion and same concentration have a junction then both Henderson's and Planck's equations for liquid junction potential (E_L) give